

A NOTE ON THE ELECTROLYTIC ESTIMATION OF LEAD AS PEROXIDE.

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Rapid and accurate estimations of lead are required to be carried out very frequently in dye manufacture and other industries. Quite a large number of methods for the estimation of lead has been described in the literature. These may be classified as (i) gravimetric, (ii) volumetric, (iii) colorimetric, (iv) potentiometric, and (v) electrolytic methods.

It is known that in the electrolysis of aqueous lead salts lead separates more completely as peroxide at the anode than as metal at the cathode (Schucht, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1883, 22, 448; Luckow, *ibid.*, 1880, 1). Under the last mentioned condition, the cathodic deposit, being in the finely divided form tends to get oxidised even by atmospheric oxygen; its estimation as peroxide might be expected therefore to give better results. Another advantage of this procedure is that other metals *e.g.* copper can be deposited and therefore estimated simultaneously on the cathode. Despite a large amount of work in this field of lead deposition, considerable uncertainty exists on the precise nature of the anodic deposit; it may be (i) pure PbO_2 , or (ii) PbO_2 mixed with some other oxides of lead. Smith ("Electro-analysis", 1918, 6th Ed., p. 111) has worked out an arbitrary factor *viz.* 0.8643 to convert PbO_2 deposited anodically during the electrolysis, into lead; the chemical conversion factor, however, is 0.8662. The aim of the present investigation is to definitely establish whether there is any necessity of using any other factor than the chemical conversion factor.

Standard solutions of lead acetate and lead nitrate were prepared and measured volumes were taken for analysis. It was found by Joshi and Subbarao (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 377) that stirring favours the formation of uniform deposits and allows the use of high current densities. Attempts to estimate lead by cathodic deposition on platinum electrode failed, since the deposit obtained from the acetate solution in presence of ammonium acetate and acetic acid could easily be washed off, or in any case, was not sufficiently adherent. Experiments were then made to estimate lead as peroxide on the anode. 25 C.c. of standard lead nitrate solution were taken in a beaker (Pb content = 0.1021 g.), 20 c.c. of conc. HNO_3 were then added and the solution made up to 100 c.c. with distilled water. A cylindrical platinum gauze was used as an anode and a rotating

platinum spiral (500-600 revolutions per minute) used as the cathode. The following were observed to be *optimum* conditions :

Voltage=3.0 to 3.1 volts ; current=3 amp. ; time = 30 minutes ; temperature=50-60° ; the wt. of PbO_2 =0.1178 g.; the wt. of Pb=0.1178 × 0.8662=0.1021 g.

Two more runs under the similar conditions gave the values for Pb as 0.1020 and 0.1019. The average value obtained was 0.1020 in agreement with the theoretical value, 0.1021. Similar agreements were obtained with cad acetate solutions in presence of 20% concentrated HNO_3 .

In all these experiments after the completion of electrolysis the platinum gauze anode with PbO_2 deposited on it, was carefully washed with distilled water, with rectified spirit and finally with ether and then dried at 190-200° for about half an hour, cooled and finally weighed.

The coincidence between the experimental and theoretical values using the ordinary chemical conversion factor 0.8662 shows that the introduction of the arbitrary factor 0.8643 is not justified. This further confirms MacInnes and Townsend's view (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 420) viz. lead peroxide is the only product of anodic oxidation and that no compound like PbO_2 , H_2O or any higher oxide is formed (*cf. Smith, loc. cit.*). The present method of estimation with the rotating electrode, is more rapid, simpler in manipulation and more accurate and can be used with advantage, for the analysis of lead salts in dye manufacture and other industries, in preference to potentiometric and other methods generally employed.

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